

Intramolecular charge transfer effects on 3,5-diaminobenzoic acid – Effect of β -cyclodextrin, pH and solvents

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Abstract : Absorption and fluorescence spectra of 3,5-diaminobenzoic acid (DABA) were analysed in different solvents, pH and β -cyclodextrin (β -CD) and compared with 3-aminobenzoic acid (ABA). A large red shifted absorption and emission maxima in non-polar solvents indicate ICT present in DABA molecule. Effects of β -CD on DABA molecule were studied in different buffer solutions (pH \sim 1, pH \sim 7 and pH \sim 10). In all the above pHs, DABA forms 1 : 1 inclusion complex. Dual luminescence is observed at pH \sim 1 and pH \sim 7 solutions which shows that intramolecular charge transfer present in both pHs. The broad spectral maximum at pH \sim 10 indicates that intramolecular proton transfer is present in DABA molecule. Proton transfer reactions in β -CD medium indicates COOH group present in the hydrophilic part, whereas amino group present in the hydrophobic part of the β -CD cavity. The present study demonstrates that in DABA, ICT interactions play a significant role in all solvents and β -CD.

Keywords : 3,5-Diaminobenzoic acid, β -cyclodextrin, intramolecular charge transfer, inclusion complex.

Introduction

Photoinduced intramolecular charge transfer (PICT) is one of the most attractive topics of interest as a primary function for photoelectronic devices¹ as well as a basic mechanism of biological and chemical energy conversion. The photoinduced charge separation is maximized when an electron donor and an acceptor groups are mutually perpendicular (in order to minimize electronic coupling between the two groups) which results in the formation of a twisted intramolecular charge transfer (TICT) state. Indeed, in few organic molecules the formation of excited TICT state followed by solvent relaxation is important in determining the overall charge transfer process². Thus, the ICT rate depends significantly on the ground state twist angle of the rotating groups³. However, some authors have suggested that the specific hydrogen bonding between the solvent and the solute is also important in order to maintain a large twist angle between the electron donor and the acceptor group⁴. Moreover, the charge separation in biological molecules is known to be coupled to proton motion which may be proton transfer process. Nevertheless, the role of the specific hydrogen bonding in the photoinduced TICT (ICT) has not been systematically investigated. Thus, the hy-

drogen bonding effect of solvent on TICT (ICT) would be an interesting subject to explore with regard to the proton transfer coupled charge transfer.

The ability of CDs to accommodate guest molecules of the appropriate size in their cavities has been utilized by many investigators to control the photophysical and photochemical properties of some molecules such as fluorescence enhancement, intramolecular excimer/exciple formation. Kim *et al.*⁵, Jiang *et al.*⁶ and others demonstrated that the TICT emission of 4-(*N,N*-diethylamino) and 4-(*N,N*-dimethylamino) benzoic acid is enhanced on complexation with a β -CD. They have attributed this property to the reduced polarity rather than to the restricted molecular motion inside the CD cavity. In this point of view, it would be interesting to see how the CD systems affect the ICT emission and the excited state geometry change of a different type of the ICT molecule.

For the past one decade, our laboratory has been actively involved in studying their photophysical properties of some organic molecules⁷⁻¹¹. Recently, we have studied solvent, pH and β -CD dependences of the photophysical properties of different molecules¹²⁻¹⁸ which shows ICT emission in the excited state. This study has

shown that the ICT interaction takes place upon excitation of 3,5-diaminobenzoic acid (DABA) as demonstrated by a large Stokes shifted fluorescence emission is polar solvents. In hydrogen bonding solvents especially the ICT emission is further shifted into the red. This has been attributed to the increased ICT emission as in the case of TICT molecules such as DMABN. The H-bonding of the carboxyl group would be facilitated by the resonance contribution from the ICT interaction in the excited state¹⁹. In our continuing efforts to explore the H-bonding effects on the ICT process of 3-aminobenzoic acid in the excited state, we have studied the effects of β -CD on the ICT fluorescence properties in aqueous solution. The β -CD cavity provides an incorporated guest molecule with a non-polar and restrictive environment²⁰. Thus, if DABA is imbedded in the inner cavity of β -CD the excited state hydrogen bonding and geometry change will be greatly affected. Further, many works demonstrated the TICT emission of 4-aminobenzoic acid derivatives⁶ but not much work was carried out in DABA. In this record we report the absorption and fluorescence characteristics of DABA in different solvents, pH and β -cyclodextrin.

Materials and method :

3,5-Diaminobenzoic acid (DABA), β -CD and all the spectrograde solvents were received from Sigma and Aldrich chemicals company and used as such. pH of solutions within the range 2.0–12.0 was adjusted by the addition of phosphate buffers (10^{-3} M) different concentration of NaOH- H_3PO_4 as this amount of buffer do not quench fluorescence of the sample and also do not alter the prototropic equilibrium under study. The solutions were prepared just before each measurement. The concentration of the DABA and ABA solutions was of the order of 2×10^{-4} M to 2×10^{-5} M and the β -CD solution was varied from 1×10^{-3} M to 1×10^{-2} M. Absorption spectral measurements were carried out with a Shimadzu UV-Visible spectrophotometer (model UV 1601 PC) and fluorescence measurements were made with a Shimadzu spectrofluorophotometer (model RF 5301). The pH values in the range 2.0–12.0 were measured on an Elico pH meter (model LI-120).

Results and discussion

Effect of β -cyclodextrin :

Table 1, Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 depict the absorption and

emission maxima of DABA (4×10^{-5} M) in pH ~ 1 , pH ~ 7 and pH ~ 10 solutions containing different concentrations of β -CD. At pH ~ 7 and pH ~ 10 , DABA exists as a carboxylic anion ($\lambda_{\text{abs}} \sim 307, 212$ nm and $\lambda_{\text{abs}} \sim 312, 217$ nm) respectively, hence we also recorded spectrum at pH ~ 1 ($\lambda_{\text{abs}} \sim 305, 277$ nm). A clear isosbestic point is present in all the pH solutions indicate that well defined 1 : 1 inclusion complex is formed between DABA and β -CD. However, the absorption and emission spectral shape are differ from each other in all the pHs indicating that different kind of inclusion complexes exists in the DABA. The formation constant for the DABA and β -CD inclusion complex has been determined by analyzing the changes in the intensity of the absorption and emission maxima with β -CD concentration. The binding constant of DABA : β -CD inclusion complex was determined by using Benesi-Hildebrand equation²¹.

At pH ~ 1 the absorption spectra does not show any marginal change in absorption maxima even in the presence of the highest β -CD concentrations used (1×10^{-2} M) indicating that, NH_3^+ group does not effectively interact with β -CD. However, a regular red shift is observed in pH ~ 7 and pH ~ 10 shows that NH_2 group interact with β -CD-OH groups. It has also been observed that both pH ~ 1 and pH ~ 7 , absorption increase with increasing concentration of β -CD whereas it is decreased at pH ~ 10 .

In order to determine the stoichiometry of the inclusion complex, the dependence on β -CD of the DABA molecule absorbance and fluorescence were analysed by using the Benesi-Hildebrand equation²¹ 1 : 1 complex (eq. 1) between both molecules and β -CD as shown below :

$$\frac{1}{I - I_0} = \frac{1}{I' - I_0} + \frac{1}{K(I - I_0)[\beta\text{-CD}]} \quad (1)$$

where K is the formation constant, I_0 is the initial absorption/fluorescence intensity of free drug molecules, I' is the absorption/fluorescence intensity of β -CD inclusion complex and I is the observed absorption/fluorescence intensity. According to eq. (1), a plot of $1/I - I_0$ versus $1/[\beta\text{-CD}]$ gives a linear line as shown in Fig. 3. This analysis reflects the formation of 1 : 1 inclusion complex between both drug molecules and β -CD complex.

Table 1. Absorption and fluorescence spectral data (nm) observed for DABA in different concentration of β -CD

Concentration of β -CD (M)	pH \sim 1			pH \sim 7			pH \sim 10		
	λ_{abs}	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{flu}	λ_{abs}	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{flu}	λ_{abs}	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{flu}
Water	305, 277, 223	2.77, 2.94, 3.91	450, 375	307, 212	3.24, 4.31	407, 392	312, 217	3.46, 4.31	418
0.002	305, 277, 223	2.92, 3.03, 3.92	450, 374	307, 212	3.27, 4.31	407, 392	313, 217	3.37, 4.32	420
0.006	305, 278, 223	2.90, 2.92, 3.89	449, 376	310, 215	3.31, 4.27	410, 392	314, 218	3.27, 4.26	420
0.010	305, 279, 223	2.95, 3.08, 3.96	448, 378	312, 217	3.31, 4.25	413, 392	316, 217	3.24, 4.24	419
Excitation wavelength	350			300			300		
Binding constant (M^{-1})	242			315			210		
ΔG (kJ mol^{-1})	-13.82			-14.49			-13.47		
							-14.32		
							-13.64		
							-14.43		

Fig. 1. Absorbance spectra of DABA in different β -CD concentrations with pH \sim 1, 7 and 10 (M): (1) 0, (2) 0.001, (3) 0.002, (4) 0.004, (5) 0.006, (6) 0.008 and (7) 0.01.

Fig. 2. Fluorescence spectra of DABA in different β -CD concentrations with pH \sim 1, 7 and 10 (M): (1) 0, (2) 0.001, (3) 0.002, (4) 0.004, (5) 0.006, (6) 0.008 and (7) 0.01.

Fig. 3. Benesi-Hildebrand plot for the complexation of DABA with β -CD : (a) plot of $1/A - A_0$ vs $1/[\beta\text{-CD}]$ and (b) plot of $1/I - I_0$ vs $1/[\beta\text{-CD}]$.

The free energy change was calculated from the formation constant (K) :

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K \quad (2)$$

The values of thermodynamic parameter ΔG for the formation of the guest molecule to β -CD is given in Table 1. As can be seen from the Table, ΔG is negative which suggests that the inclusion proceeded simultaneously at 303 K. The experimental results indicate that the inclusion reaction of β -CD with the above drugs are an exothermic process.

The effect of β -CD on the fluorescence spectra of DABA is more pronounced than the corresponding effect on the absorption spectra. Fig. 2 depicts the emission spectra of DABA pH ~1, pH ~7 and pH ~10 solutions containing different concentrations of β -CD. With an increasing the β -CD concentration, the fluorescence intensities increased at pH ~1, whereas decreased at pH ~7 and pH ~10. In β -CD free aqueous solution single emission maximum was observed at pH ~10 ($\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim 418$ nm), whereas dual emission was observed at pH ~1 ($\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim 375$,

450 nm) and pH ~7 ($\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim 400, 410$ nm). In pH ~7, with an increasing the β -CD concentration, a slight red shift was observed in the emission maxima ($\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim 407$ to 413 nm), while no significant shift was noticed in pH ~1 ($\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim 375, 450$ nm) and pH ~10 ($\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim 419$ nm). In β -CD, the spectral red shifted emission at pH ~7 suggests that carbonyl group is located within the non-polar cavity of β -CD, whereas NH_2 group is located in polar medium. At pH ~1, the dual emission noticed in the β -CD medium established that amino group is deeply entrapped in the β -CD cavity. Since dipole-dipole interaction between β -CD-OH and amino group is lowered in the less polar environment (hydrophobic part) a ICT observed in pH ~1 solution.

In pH ~1 and pH ~7 solutions, a typical dual emission can be seen even though the emission intensity of the longer wavelength (LW) is more or less equal in pH ~7 but it is high in the case of pH ~1. The weak shorter wavelength (SW) emission has been presumably ascribed to the stabilization of the highly polar ICT state by strong dipole-dipole interaction with water (Fig. 4) and consequent rapid non-radiative transition to the ground state. With an addition of β -CD, both the SW and LW emission is increased at pH ~1 whereas gradually decreased at pH ~7. It is also noteworthy that in pH ~1, the ICT emission increased at the same wavelength with gradual increase of fluorescence intensity. The fluorescence intensity ratio of the ICT band to the normal band (I_a/I_b) is constant at pH ~1, whereas at pH ~7 the I_a/I_b ratio is decreased as the concentration of β -CD increases. In other words, as the concentration of β -CD increases, I_a/I_b ratio at pH ~7 decreases in contrast to the pH ~1 solution. It can be taken as further evidence for the formation of DABA : β -CD inclusion complexes, that the initial changes of the I_a/I_b ratio in both pH ~1 and pH ~7 levels are equal in high β -CD concentration. The ICT emission is not observed at pH ~10 and the spectral changes different from other pH solutions suggesting the structural geometry of the DABA/ β -CD inclusion complex is different from the other buffer solutions. In other words, it seems to be obvious that the carboxyl anion is dramatically affected the ICT behaviour of DABA.

On increasing the β -CD concentrations in pH ~10 buffer solutions, the absorbance as well as emission in-

Fig. 4. CAChe-DFT optimized structure and proposed inclusion complex structure of DABA.

tensity decreased at the same wavelength suggesting DABA molecule is deeply encapsulated in the β -CD cavity. Both the absorption and emission maxima slightly red shifted in pH ~ 7 solutions indicating protonation took place in the carboxylate anion. This implication is based on the following reasons : the large rim of β -CD containing 14 secondary hydroxyl groups provides an environment qualitatively similar to polyhydroxy alcohols²¹⁻²⁵. Further it is well known that β -CD is a very good proton donor²³⁻³¹ and this may provide protons for the protonation to the carboxylic anion. More interestingly in higher β -CD concentrations, the absorption and emission maxima and the spectral shape of DABA is more or less same in pH ~ 1 and pH ~ 7 solutions are different which concludes different type of inclusion complexes are formed. Moreover, it is well known that substituents of aromatic ring have tendency to form hydrogen bond with the hydroxyl groups of the β -CD edges. The energy involved in such hydrogen bond interaction is responsible for the higher or lower binding constants compared to those of the substituted or unsubstituted molecules.

The LW emission is not observed in pH ~ 10 buffer solution is explained as follows : At pH ~ 10, the presence of carboxyl anion prevents the formation of ICT emission. The broad longer wavelength emission in β -CD free aqueous solution suggests intramolecular proton transfer (IPT) is formed. The decrease in full width at half a maximum (FWHM) with increasing β -CD concentration further supported this prediction. The similar results on 3,5-dihydroxy benzoic acid also support this idea²⁵. Moreover we have already reported that if carboxyl or amino groups are deeply entrapped in the CD cavity, the absorption and emission maxima should be blue shifted than that of aqueous medium because the interior part of the CD cavity provides a non-polar environment like cyclohexane²⁵⁻²⁹. Further one should expect, if carboxyl anion present in the hydrophilic part of the β -CD cavity protonation should takes place in this anion. In β -CD, if protonation takes place in the carboxyl anion, red shift should be observed and the absorption and emission maxima should be similar to pH ~ 7 me-

dium, because under this environment carboxylic anion is present. The results in Table 1 indicate in β -CD the carboxyl anion absorption and emission maxima is red shifted than in aqueous medium. The above findings confirm in DABA, amino group is entrapped in the interior part of the β -CD cavity and COOH group is present in the hydrophilic part of the β -CD cavity. In other words, both the carboxyl and amino groups can be hydrogen bonded with water, but the orientations of those two groups can be different with regard to facing water molecule by forming different patterns of β -CD inclusion complexes.

Effect of acid-base concentrations :

To get a better understanding of the CD environment, the effect of acid-base concentrations in the range of $H_0 - 5$ to H_{-10} on the absorption and fluorescence spectra of DABA were studied in water and β -CD solutions. The relevant data are given in Table 2. In the pH range 2.5 absorption maximum resemble with the spectrum observed in non-aqueous solvents and thus assigned to be neutral

Table 2. Various prototropic maxima (absorption and fluorescence) of DABA in aqueous and β -CD medium

Species	DABA			
	Aqueous medium		β -CD medium	
	λ_{abs}	λ_{flu}	λ_{abs}	λ_{flu}
Monocation	367, 305, 277, 224	374, 474	367, 305, 271, 224	376, 450
Neutral	314, 219	483	313, 219	483
Monoanion	307, 218	407	313, 218	413
Dianion	313, 230	417		
Trianion	318, 230	Q		

species. Above pH ~ 3 the absorption spectrum of DABA is regularly blue shifted (313 nm to 305 nm) in comparison to the neutral species and is assigned to monoanion formed by deprotonating the COOH group. This is because the pK_a value for the deprotonation of aromatic carboxylic groups falls in this range³¹. With an increase in the pH from 4.5 to 11, the absorption maximum is again red shifted from 305 nm to 317 nm indicates IPT

present in this molecule. Further increase in the pH from 4.5 the absorption spectrum of DABA gets red shifted in comparison to monoanion. This has been assigned to the dianion obtained by further deprotonating the amino group. It is well-known fact deprotonation of carboxyl group gives blue shifted absorption maxima where as deprotonation of amino group gives red shifted absorption maxima³¹. On decreasing pH from 4, the absorption band starts blue shifting at $H_0 \sim 0.8$ and reached maximum value at $H_0 \sim 0.2$. This spectrum has a maximum close to that of benzoic acid. Hence, the blue shifts observed in the absorption maxima, which increase of hydrogen ion concentration suggest the formation of dication in the amino group²⁶⁻²⁸. Further increasing acid concentration, no significant absorption shift noticed.

With an increase in pH from 3 to 6, fluorescence spectrum is largely blue shifted (445 nm to 410 nm) and the largely blue shifted fluorescence band at pH ~ 5 is assigned to monoanion formed by the deprotonation of the carboxyl group. Hence, the weak 445 nm fluorescence band at pH ~ 2 is assigned to monocation formed by the protonation of amino group. Further acid concentration is increased from $H_0 \sim 1.0$ the fluorescence band is slightly red shifted with the maximum of 458 nm indicating protonation takes place at carboxyl group. The fluorescence spectra of DABA (410 nm) in the pH range from 3 to 6 is assigned to the monoanion species because these fluorescence spectra agree with ABA. Above pH ~ 13 , due to formation of dianion, the emission maxima are quenched in this molecule.

Effect of solvents :

To analyze the β -CD-induced changes in the absorption and fluorescence spectra of DABA, we also studied in different solvents and compared with 3-aminobenzoic acid (ABA). The experimental results are compiled in Table 3. There is no absorption maximum observed in cyclohexane, because the solubility of DABA is very low in non-polar solvent. The absorption spectra of DABA and ABA in all the solvents consist of two absorption bands. Both longer (~ 340 nm) and shorter (~ 220 nm) wavelength bands are broad and exhibit a slight red shift upon increasing the solvent polarity from ether to acetonitrile. However, compared to aprotic solvents the absorption spectra of DABA is blue shifted with increasing

Table 3. Absorption and fluorescence spectral data (nm) observed for DABA and 3ABA in different solvents

Solvents	DABA				3ABA			
	λ_{abs}	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{flu}	Stokes shift	λ_{abs}	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{flu}	Stokes shift
Cyclohexane	338, 222	sat	350	1014	319, 220	sat	360	3568
1,4-Dioxane	341, 223	3.75, 3.62	412	5171	327, 222	3.57, 3.26	388	4808
Acetonitrile	339, 224	3.71, 4.63	426	6024	322, 222	3.67, 3.42	396	5755
2-Propanol	334, 222	3.65, 4.58	465	8435	317, 221	3.70, 3.38	430	8241
Methanol	332, 221	3.74, 4.68	479	9244	318, 221	3.88, 3.42	430	8191
Water	307, 212	3.48, 4.54	407	8003	308, 221	3.31, 3.56	440	9740
Dipole moment (D)				3.65				3.42
Onsager cavity radius (\AA)				3.75				3.42

sat – saturation.

proton donor capacity of the solvents. Because of dispersive interactions, from ether to acetonitrile a red shift is observed in the absorption spectrum while blue shift observed in protic solvents indicates these solvents act as proton donors. Both the UV bands ($\pi-\pi^*$) suffer a small solvent shifts on changing the polar substituent attached to the phenyl moiety, a behaviour which is characteristic of the type of electronic transition corresponding to these bands. On the other hand, in the S_1 state, the compound display a broad visible band in emission (with in the range 350–480 nm). This band can be assigned to ($\pi-\pi^*$) transition involving a considerable charge transfer (CT) character. Such a CT originates mainly from the NH_2 group to the carbonyl group which is characterized by a high electron accepting character^{32,33}. In S_1 state, the polarity of the amino group is further increased due to the increased charge transfer interaction from the amino group to carboxyl group and NH_2 group act as a better proton donor, thus a continuous red shift observed in the emission spectra which is due to the dispersive interactions and proton accepting nature of all the solvents.

The absorption spectrum of DABA and ABA in water (at pH ~ 7) is largely blue shifted than other solvents. Acidic pH ~ 3 does not dramatically affect the appearance of the spectrum except for a red shift. This effect of the pH on the absorption spectrum indicates that the carboxyl group is ionized in pH ~ 7 , because deprotonation of carboxyl group is blue shifted. The spectra do not suffer important changes in their shape when using polar and non-polar solvents. In all cases, the absorption spectra resemble that of ABA and the main differences being the blue shift of the DABA. This similarity points due to

the conjugation between the amino and carboxyl groups^{26–28}.

Fig. 5 depicts the fluorescence spectrum of the DABA in selected solvents and the relevant data compiled in

Fig. 5. Fluorescence spectra of 3,5-diaminobenzoic acid in selected solvents at 303 K : (1) cyclohexane, (2) dioxane, (3) acetonitrile, (4) 2-propanol, (5) methanol and (6) water.

Table 3. A large red shift observed in the fluorescence band maximum with increasing polarity and hydrogen band forming tendency of the solvents indicates the increase in the delocalization of the π -cloud of the carbonyl group and the lone pair of the amino group throughout the aromatic moiety in the S_1 state. A large Stokes shifted emission band observed in different solvents and this band is very sensitive to change in solvent polarity suggesting that greater charge transfer takes place between the carbonyl and amino group in the S_1 state than in the S_0 state.

In non-polar solvent, the emission intensity of DABA is very weak and in polar solvent the emission maxima is

red shifted (480 nm) than 4ABA (440 nm). This is probably, in DABA the *meta* directing carbonyl group increases the ICT emission. In the presence of solvents more polar than cyclohexane widens, with increasing Stokes shifted emission maxima. The emission in water is strongly pH dependent with the Stokes shift reaching its maximum value in acidic aqueous solutions. The broad and large Stokes shifted emission at acidic pH is common in molecules having an electron withdrawing group such as carboxyl group attached to an aromatic nucleus. In the excited state, amino and carbonyl group are more acidic and basic respectively, than in the ground state. Thus, the basic nature of carbonyl group can accept a proton from the amino group and through delocalization of the aromatic ring. However, the nature of such an emission is not always easy to ascertain, since it can be the result of a variety of causes including dimer formation in the ground state (or other kinds of aggregates) excimer emission or charge transfer processes³⁴.

In the case of DABA, the fact that the broad band is also appear at alkaline pH could ruled out the possibility of DABA forming dimers in the ground state (linked by H-bonding), which gives rise to excimer emission upon excitation³⁴. These dimers cannot form if the carboxylate group is ionized. Even at concentrations as low as $1 \times 10^{-6} M$ the broad emission can be detected. Further, the presence of amino group in the *meta* position with respect to carbonyl group which strongly undergo ICT emission in the S_1 state.

Excimer emission could also result from some kind of packing of the following molecules, even if hydrogen bonding is not the driving force^{35,36}. This is a planar molecule a feature that is known to facilitate this type of emission as in *p*-dimethylaminobenzoic acid^{35,36}. However, this mechanism must be rejected as will be explained in the following reason when discussing the influence of CDs on the DABA fluorescence. Higher Stokes shift observed in the fluorescence spectrum of DABA, in polar solvents confirms that the emission observed from the ICT state and not from the normal or neutral species. The largely red shifted emission spectra in polar solvents would indicate a primarily dipolar interaction between the solute and the solvent molecules. This is due to the H-bonding is added to the dipolar contribution in polar solvents with the subsequent stabilization of the CT state. Further,

DABA is a multimolecular process, the emission of a state with a high ICT stabilized by H-bonding with the solvent³². In such a state, the donor group is the NH_2 group of the DABA molecule and the acceptor group is carbonyl group.

In DABA, the energy of locally excited state and charge transfer are equally affected, hence it gives single emission maxima at longer wavelength. The large red shifted emission maxima in all the solvents would indicate a dipolar interaction between the solute and solvent molecules. In non-polar solvent, the ionic form is less soluble, hence it gives weakly fluorescent, i.e. the carboxylate anion already containing a negative charge will not readily accept a second negative charge necessary for the resonance interaction and consequently the emission is weak in cyclohexane³⁵.

Since ICT forces play an important role in the excited state, the emission maxima of DABA is largely red shifted in polar solvents than *ortho* and *para* aminobenzoic acids. This conclusion is based on the following reasons : (i) like absorption spectrum, the fluorescence spectrum in each solvent is broader and that is having broader full width at half the maximum height (FWHM). The FWHM of the fluorescence spectrum increases in polar solvents suggested that ICT present in DABA molecule and this ICT increases in the protic solvents, (ii) dipole moment is largely increased in the S_1 state, (iii) *meta* directing carbonyl group increases ICT emission, (iv) at higher β -CD concentrations (pH \sim 1 and pH \sim 7) a dual emission is appeared and (v) geometry of DABA and ABA is optimized using the DFT method, it shows bond angle is deviated from 120° is confirmed steric effect present in 2ABA, whereas the bond angle is not changed in DABA (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

On the basis of the above discussions, it is clear that as long as the carboxyl group is present in the hydrophilic part, the magnitude of the contribution of the fast relaxations process to form the ICT state in the β -CD inclusion complex increases. The smaller size and presence of different ionic species of DABA is responsible for the formation of different inclusion complexes in the β -CD solutions. As shown in Fig. 4 one of the two different inclusion complexes could be the type I complex (pH \sim 1 and pH \sim 7), in which the COOH group located in the hydrophilic part and the other could be the type II complex in which NH_2 group is more deeply located in the hydrophobic part of the cavity. At pH \sim 1, type I complex is formed, whereas at pH \sim 7 in low β -CD concentrations type II complex is more favorable than type I. However, at higher β -CD concentration (pH \sim 7), type I complex is favorable because protonation takes place in the carboxyl group. Supporting this at pH \sim 7, absorption and normal maxima are red shifted with increasing β -CD concentration. As the β -CD concentration is increased at pH \sim 10 a small portion of type II complex is formed.

Considering that TICT emission was observed in *N,N*-dimethylamino benzoic acid and *N,N*-diethylamino benzoic acid^{5,6} and aminobenzoic acids²⁶⁻²⁸ it can be concluded that the restriction or the increased viscosity in the β -CD cavity does not affect the formation the ICT state. The enhancement of the ICT emission of β -CD solution should be due to the reduced polarity of the β -CD environment as proposed by Krishnamoorthy *et al.*³¹ for *N,N*-dimethylamino benzonitrile and Rajendiran *et al.* for aminobenzoic acids²⁵⁻²⁸. In the less polar environment the ICT state and the Franck-Condon state is increased. This is supported by the formation of ICT state of DHB upon complexation with β -CD. The increased energy gap causes a decrease in the non-radiative transitions from the ICT state so that ICT emission is enhanced. Such an increase in the energy gap is attributable to the reduced dipole-dipole interaction of the ICT state in the β -CD cavity.

The difference in the inclusion process is also responsible for the different association constants. The large association constant at pH \sim 1 and pH \sim 7 implies that of DABA is more deeply embedded in the β -CD cavity than at pH \sim 10. The gradual enhancement in the ICT emission with increasing β -CD concentration is consistent with

this speculation. In other words, at pH \sim 1 and pH \sim 7, DABA is more deeply entrapped in the non-polar β -CD cavity than pH \sim 10. Thus, the enhancement of the ICT emission in both pH \sim 1 and pH \sim 7 solutions indicates that the energy barrier is not affected by the entrapment of DABA in the non-polar β -CD cavity. From this observation, it can be concluded that the energy barrier for the formation of the ICT state is governed by the hydrogen bonding between the carboxyl group and water. As long as the H-bonding between the carboxyl group and water is effective, the energy barrier for the ICT is not changed. As discussed above the orientation of DABA inclusion complex at pH \sim 1 and pH \sim 7 is different to that at pH \sim 10.

This is further supported by using semi empirical quantum calculations. PC-model program is used to find the initial geometry of the inclusion complex. This program helped us to draw the structure of the inclusion complex. The ground state geometry of DABA and β -CD are optimized using CAChe-DFT method. The internal diameters of the β -CD is approximately 6.5 Å and its height is 7.8 Å. Considering the shape and dimensions of β -CD (Fig. 4) DABA can be completely embedded in the β -CD cavity. Because the vertical distance between OH-OH is 5.58 Å and $\text{H}_4\text{-O}_2$ is 6.22 Å, these values are less than the β -CD inside cavity value (6.5 Å). Since the length of DABA is lower than that of upper/lower rim of β -CD, the carboxyl and hydroxyl groups attached benzene ring may be present inside the β -CD cavity as shown in Fig. 5. These finding reveals that DABA molecule is embedded in the β -CD cavity.

Conclusions

The following conclusions can be arrived at from the above studies : (i) a large red shifted absorption and emission maxima observed in non-polar solvents indicates ICT present in DABA molecule, (ii) DABA forms 1 : 1 complex with β -CD, (iii) proton transfer reactions in β -CD medium indicates, COOH group present in the hydrophilic part of the β -CD cavity whereas amino group present in the hydrophobic part of the β -CD cavity and (iv) the above studies demonstrate that in DABA, ICT interactions plays a significant role in β -CD aqueous/polar solvents.

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References

- E. Ishow, R. Guillot, G. Buntinx and O. Poizat, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 2012, **234**, 27.
- Y. M. Issa, H. B. Hassib, H. E. Abdelaal and I. M. Kenawi, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2011, **79**, 1364.
- Y. Zhu, S. Guang, X. Su, H. Xu and D. Xu, *Dyes and Pigments*, 2013, **97**, 175.
- B. K. Paul, A. Samanta, S. Kar and N. Guchhait, *J. Luminescence*, 2010, **130**, 1258.
- T. H. Kim, D. W. Cho, M. Yoon and D. Kim, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1996, **100**, 15670.
- Y. B. Jiang, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 1995, **88**, 109.
- T. Sivasankar, A. Antony Muthu Prabhu, M. Karthick and N. Rajendiran, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 2012, **1028**, 57.
- A. Antony Muthu Prabhu, S. Siva, R. K. Sankaranarayanan and N. Rajendiran, *J. Fluorescence*, 2010, **20**, 43.
- A. Antony Muthu Prabhu, S. Siva, R. K. Sankaranarayanan and N. Rajendiran, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2010, **49**, 407.
- A. Antony Muthu Prabhu, S. Siva, R. K. Sankaranarayanan and N. Rajendiran, *J. Mol. Liq.*, 2011, **161**, 107.
- A. Antony Muthu Prabhu, V. K. Subramanian and N. Rajendiran, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2012, **96**, 95.
- R. K. Sankaranarayanan, A. Antony Muthu Prabhu, S. Siva and N. Rajendiran, *J. Incl. Phenom. Macrocycl. Chem.*, 2010, **67**, 461.
- G. Venkatesh, A. Antony Muthu Prabhu and N. Rajendiran, *J. Fluorescence*, 2011, **21**, 1485.
- A. Antony Muthu Prabhu, S. Siva, R. K. Sankaranarayanan and N. Rajendiran, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2009, **74**, 484.
- A. Antony Muthu Prabhu, R. K. Sankaranarayanan, G. Venkatesh and N. Rajendiran, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2012, **116**, 9061.
- A. Antony Muthu Prabhu and N. Rajendiran, *J. Fluorescence*, 2012, **22**, 1461.
- J. Premakumari, G. Allan Gnana Roy, A. Antony Muthu Prabhu, G. Venkatesh, V. K. Subramanian and N. Rajendiran, *Phys. Chem. Liq.*, 2011, **49**, 108.
- A. Antony Muthu Prabhu, G. Venkatesh and N. Rajendiran, *J. Solution Chem.*, 2010, **39**, 1061.
- M. Smoluch, H. Joshi, A. Gerssen, C. Gooijer and G. van der Zwan, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 2005, **109**, 535.
- K. Kalyanasundaram, "Photochemistry in Microheterogeneous Systems", Academic Press, New York, 1987.
- A. Benesi and J. H. Hildebrand, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 2703.
- S. Das, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2002, **361**, 21.
- S. Sandra and S. K. Dogra, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 1996, **101**, 221.
- T. Stalin, R. Anitha Devi and N. Rajendiran, *Spectrochimica Acta (A)*, 2005, **61**, 2495.
- M. L. Bender and M. Komiyama, in "Cyclodextrin Chemistry", Springer-Verlag, New York, 1978.
- S. Siva, A. Antony Muthu Prabhu, R. K. Sankaranarayanan and N. Rajendiran, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2009, **48**, 1515.
- T. Stalin and N. Rajendiran, *Chem. Phys.*, 2006, **322**, 311.
- T. Stalin and N. Rajendiran, *J. Incl. Phenom. Macrocycl. Chem.*, 2006, **55**, 21.
- T. Stalin and N. Rajendiran, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 2006, **182**, 137.
- J. K. Dey and S. K. Dogra, *Chem. Phys.*, 1990, **143**, 97.
- N. Rajendiran and M. Swaminathan, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 1995, **90**, 109.
- G. Krishnamoorthy and S. K. Dogra, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 1999, **123**, 109.
- P. R. Sainz Rozas, J. R. Isasi, M. Sanchez, G. Tardajas and G. G. Gaitano, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2004, **108**, 392.
- N. M. Rageh, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2004, **60**, 103.
- J. K. Dey, J. L. Haynes, A. K. Chandra and I. M. Warner, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 1997, **101**, 2271.
- Y. Kim, M. Yoon and D. Kim, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 2001, **138**, 167.
- Y. B. Jiang, *Appl. Spectrosc.*, 1994, **48**, 1169.